

PSEUDO W_3 -CURVATURE TENSOR ON RIEMANNIAN MANIFOLD

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we introduce a new tensor named pseudo W_3 -curvature tensor \tilde{W}_3 which generalizes the notion of W_3 -curvature tensor Pokhariyal and Mishra (1973). We deduced same basic properties of pseudo W_3 -curvature tensor.

Keywords: Curvature tensor, Riemannian manifold, W_3 -curvature, Conservative pseudo W_3 -curvature tensor.

1. INTRODUCTION

In 1973 Pokhariyal and Mishra introduced W_3 -curvature tensors of the type (1, 3) and studied its relativistic significance and the expression is

$$W_3(Y, Z)U = R(Y, Z)U - \frac{1}{(n-1)}[Ric(Y, U)Z - g(Z, U)QY]. \quad (1.1)$$

The Equation (1.1) can be put in (0, 4) types

$${}^*W_3(Y, Z, U, V) = {}^*R(Y, Z, U, V) - \frac{1}{(n-1)}[Ric(Y, U)g(Z, V) - g(Z, U)Ric(Y, V)], \quad (1.2)$$

where ${}^*W_3(Y, Z, U, V) = g(W_3(Y, Z)U, V)$ and ${}^*R(Y, Z, U, V) = g(R(Y, Z)U, V)$,

' R is the curvature tensor of the type (0, 4), Ric is the Riccitenor of the type (0,2) defined by $Ric(X, Y) = g(QX, Y)$ and Q is the Ricci operator of the type (1,1). This tensor has been recently studied in different ambient spaces such as weakly W_3 -symmetric manifolds by Hui (2011), W_3 -symmetric K-contact Riemannian manifold by Njui, Moindi and Pokhariyal (2018), Moindi, Pombo and Nzimbi (2020) with the title "Eta-Ricci soliton on W_3 -symmetric manifolds", W_3 -curvature tensor on Relativistic space times by Shenawy, Abu-Doria and Syied (2020), semi-generalized W_3 -recurrent manifolds by Lalnunsiami and Singh (2021), A study of W_3 -curvature tensor in LP-Sasakian manifold by Isaiah, Moinadi and Nzimbi (2022) and others.

In 2013, Mantica and Suh introduced anew curvature tensor of the type (1, 3) in an n-dimensional Riemannian manifold (M^n, g) , denoted by Q_1 and defined by

$$Q_1(X, Y)Z = R(X, Y)Z - \frac{\phi}{(n-1)}[g(Y, Z)X - g(X, Z)Y],$$

where ϕ is an arbitrary scalar function.

Such a tensor Q_1 , is known as Q_1 -Curvature tensor. The notion of Q_1 -tensor is also suitable to reinterpret some differential structures on a Riemannian manifold. The notion of semi- projective curvature tensor were introduced by De and Majhi (2018) and its curvature tensor under the entitled

'On pseudo semi-projective symmetric manifolds', given by

$$P(X, Y)U = R(X, Y)U - \frac{\phi}{(n-1)}[Ric(Y, U)X - Ric(X, U)Y], \quad (1.3)$$

where ' ϕ is an arbitrary scalar function. If ' $\phi = 1$ then equation (1.3) reduces to projective curvature tensor. This justifies its nomenclature. If ' $\phi = 0$, then semi-projective curvature tensor and curvature tensor are equivalent.

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Motivated by the above studies in the present paper we define pseudo W_3 -curvature tensor \tilde{W}_3 of the type (1, 3) as follows:

$$\tilde{W}_3(Y, Z)U = R(Y, Z)U - \frac{a}{(n-1)}[Ric(Y, U)Z - g(Z, U)QY], \quad (1.4)$$

where a is an arbitrary constant, not equal to zero. We prefer the name ‘pseudo W_3 - curvature tensor \tilde{W}_3 , since it is clear that for $a = 1$, \tilde{W}_3 -curvature tensor reduces to W_3 - curvature tensor.

We can express (1.4) as follows:

$$\tilde{W}_3(Y, Z, U, V) = 'R(Y, Z, U, V) - \frac{a}{(n-1)}[Ric(Y, U)g(Z, V) - Ric(Y, V)g(Z, U)], \quad (1.5)$$

where $'\tilde{W}_3(Y, Z, U, V) = g(W_3(Y, Z)U, V)$ and $'R(Y, Z, U, V) = g(R(Y, Z)U, V)$.

After introduction and preliminaries we find, algebraic properties of Ricci tensor. In next section we studied Ricci symmetric property and conservative property of \tilde{W}_3 .

2. PRELIMINARIES

In this section, some algebraic properties are derived which will be useful to the study of \tilde{W}_3 . Let $\{e_i\}$ be an orthonormal basis of the tangent space at each point of the manifold, manifold are given by the following

$$Ric(X, Y) = \sum_{i=1}^n 'R(e_i, X, Y, e_i) \text{ and } r = \sum_{i=1}^n Ric(e_i, e_i) = \sum_{i=1}^n g(Qe_i, e_i).$$

From (1.5), we have

$$\tilde{W}_3(Z, Y, U, V) = 'R(Z, Y, U, V) - \frac{a}{(n-1)}[Ric(Z, U)g(Y, V) - g(Y, U)Ric(Z, V)]. \quad (2.1)$$

Adding (1.5) and (2.1), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{W}_3(Y, Z, U, V) + \tilde{W}_3(Z, Y, U, V) = & -\frac{a}{(n-1)}[Ric(Y, U)g(Z, V) - Ric(Y, V)g(Z, U) \\ & + Ric(Z, U)g(Y, V) - Ric(Z, V)g(Y, U)]. \end{aligned} \quad (2.2)$$

Again from (1.5), we have

$$'\tilde{W}_3(Y, Z, V, U) = 'R(Y, Z, V, U) - \frac{a}{(n-1)}[Ric(Y, V)g(Z, U) - Ric(Y, U)g(Z, V)]. \quad (2.3)$$

Adding (1.5) and (2.3), we get

$$\tilde{W}_3(Y, Z, U, V) + '\tilde{W}_3(Y, Z, V, U) = 0. \quad (2.4)$$

Similarly, we have

$$\tilde{W}_3(U, V, Y, Z) = 'R(U, V, Y, Z) - \frac{a}{(n-1)}[Ric(U, Y)g(V, Z) - Ric(U, Z)g(V, Y)]. \quad (2.5)$$

From (1.5) and (2.5), we get

$$\tilde{W}_3(Y, Z, U, V) - \tilde{W}_3(U, V, Y, Z) = \frac{a}{(n-1)}[Ric(U, Z)g(V, Y) - Ric(Y, V)g(Z, U)]. \quad (2.6)$$

Further taking the cyclic rotation of Y, Z, U in equation (1.5), we get

$$'\tilde{W}_3(Z, U, Y, V) = 'R(Z, U, Y, V) - \frac{a}{(n-1)}[Ric(Z, Y)g(U, V) - Ric(Z, V)g(U, Y)] \quad (2.7)$$

and $'\tilde{W}_3(U, Y, Z, V) = 'R(U, Y, Z, V) - \frac{a}{(n-1)}[Ric(U, Z)g(Y, V) - Ric(U, V)g(Y, Z)]. \quad (2.8)$

Adding equations (1.5), (2.7) and (2.8) and using the fact $'R(Y, Z, U, V) + 'R(Z, U, V, Y) + 'R(U, Y, Z, V) = 0$ in resulting equation, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{W}_3(Y, Z, U, V) + \tilde{W}_3(Z, U, Y, V) + \tilde{W}_3(U, Y, Z, V) = & -\frac{a}{(n-1)}[Ric(Y, U)g(Z, V) \\ & - Ric(Y, V)g(Z, U) + Ric(Z, Y)g(U, V) - Ric(Z, V)g(U, Y) + Ric(U, Z)g(Y, V) \\ & - Ric(U, V)g(Y, Z)]. \end{aligned} \quad (2.9)$$

Now differentiating covariantly (1.5) with respect to X , we get

$$(D_X \tilde{W}_3)(Y, Z, U, V) = (D_X 'R)(Y, Z, U, V) - \frac{a}{(n-1)}[D_X Ric(Y, U)g(Z, V) - D_X Ric(Y, V)g(Z, U)]. \quad (2.10)$$

Similarly, we have

$$(D_Y \tilde{W}_3)(Z, X, U, V) = (D_Y 'R)(Z, X, U, V) - \frac{a}{(n-1)}[D_Y Ric(Z, U)g(X, V) - D_Y Ric(Z, V)g(X, U)] \quad (2.11)$$

and $(D_Z \tilde{W}_3)(X, Y, U, V) = (D_Z 'R)(X, Y, U, V) - \frac{a}{(n-1)}[D_Z Ric(X, U)g(Y, V) - D_Z Ric(X, V)g(Y, U)]. \quad (2.12)$

We know that Bianchi's second identity for the Riemanniansenseas

$$(D_X 'R)(Y, Z, U, V) + (D_Y 'R)(Z, X, U, V) + (D_Z 'R)(X, Y, U, V) = 0. \quad (2.13)$$

Therefore, adding (2.10), (2.11), (2.12) and using (2.13) in resulting equation, we have

$$(D_X \tilde{W}_3)(Y, Z, U, V) + (D_Y \tilde{W}_3)(Z, X, U, V) + (D_Z \tilde{W}_3)(X, Y, U, V) = \frac{-a}{(n-1)} \\ \{[D_X Ric(Y, U)g(Z, V) - D_X Ric(Y, V)g(Z, U)] + [D_Y Ric(Z, U)g(X, V) \\ - D_Y Ric(Z, V)g(X, U)] + [D_Z Ric(X, U)g(Y, V) - D_Z Ric(X, V)g(Y, U)]\}. \quad (2.14)$$

From (1.5), we have

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \tilde{W}_3(Y, Z, e_i, e_i) = (C_3^1 \tilde{W}_3)(Y, Z) = 0. \quad (2.15)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \tilde{W}_3(e_i, e_i, Y, Z) = 0.$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \tilde{W}_3(e_i, Z, U, e_i) = (C_1^1 \tilde{W}_3)(Z, U) = Ric(Z, U) \left[1 - \frac{a}{(n-1)}\right] + \frac{ra}{(n-1)}g(Z, U). \quad (2.16)$$

and $\sum_{i=1}^n \tilde{W}_3(Y, e_i, e_i, V) = (C_2^1 \tilde{W}_3)(Y, V) = (1+a)Ric(Y, V), \quad (2.17)$

where $(C_1^1 \tilde{W}_3)$, $(C_2^1 \tilde{W}_3)$ and $(C_3^1 \tilde{W}_3)$ denotes the contraction with respect to Y , Z , and U respectively.

In the view of (2.2), (2.4), (2.9) and (2.14), we have the following theorem

Theorem 3.1: Pseudo W_3 -curvature tensor on a Riemannian manifold is

- i. Skew-symmetric in first pair of slot if and only if either $a = 0$ or Einstein.
- ii. Skew-symmetric in second pair of slot.
- iii. Symmetric in last pair of slot if and only if either $a = 0$ or Einstein.
- iv. Satisfies first Bianchi's identity if and only if either $a = 0$ or Einstein.
- v. Satisfies second Bianchi's identity if $dr(X) = 0$, provided $a \neq 0$.

3. PSEUDO W_3 -FLAT RIEMANNIAN MANIFOLD

For flat manifold, we have

$$\tilde{W}_3(Y, Z, U, V) = 0. \quad (3.1)$$

Thus from (1.5) and (3.1), we have

$$R(Y, Z, U, V) = \frac{a}{(n-1)} [Ric(Y, U)g(Z, V) - Ric(Y, V)g(Z, U)]. \quad (3.2)$$

Putting e_i for Y and V in (3.2), we get

$$R(e_i, Z, U, e_i) = \frac{a}{(n-1)} [Ric(e_i, U)g(Z, e_i) - Ric(e_i, e_i)g(Z, U)].$$

That is

$$Ric(Z, U) = \frac{a}{(n-1)} [Ric(Z, U) - rg(Z, U)]. \quad (3.3)$$

Hence (3.3) gives

$$Ric(Z, U) = \frac{-ra}{(n-1-a)}g(Z, U). \quad (3.4)$$

Equation (3.4) shows that manifold is Einstein.

Further again contracting (3.4), we get

$$r(1+a) = 0. \quad (3.5)$$

Hence from (3.5), we get

Either $r = 0$ or $1+a = 0$. But $1+a \neq 0$.

Thus, we have the following

Theorem 3.1: If the Riemannian admits flat pseudo W_3 -curvature, then the scalar curvature vanishes, provided $a \neq -1$.

4. PSEUDO W_3 -SYMMETRIC MANIFOLD

Differentiating covariant equation (1.4), we with respect to X

$$(D_X \tilde{W}_3)(Y, Z)U = (D_X R)(Y, Z)U - \frac{a}{(n-1)} [D_X Ric(Y, U)Z - g(Z, U)(D_X Q)Y]. \quad (4.1)$$

Since the pseudo W_3 -curvature tensor is symmetric, i.e. $(D_X \tilde{W}_3)(Y, Z)U = 0$. Hence from (4.1), we have

$$(D_X R)(Y, Z)U = \frac{a}{(n-1)} [D_X Ric(Y, U)Z - g(Z, U)(D_X Q)Y]. \quad (4.2)$$

Contracting (4.2) with respect to Y , we get

$$(D_X Ric)(Z, U) = \frac{a}{(n-1)} [(D_Z Ric)(Y, U) - g(Z, U)dr(X)]. \quad (4.3)$$

Equation (4.3) gives

$$(D_X Ric)(Z, U) \left(1 - \frac{a}{(n-1)}\right) = \frac{a}{(n-1)} [-g(Z, U) dr(X)].$$

Or $(D_X Ric)(Z, U) = \frac{-a}{(n-1-a)} g(Z, U) dr(X).$ (4.4)

Again contracting Z and U in (4.4), we get

$$dr(X) = 0, 1 + a \neq 0. \tag{4.5}$$

Hence from the above discussion, we can state the following theorem:

Theorem 4.1: If the pseudo W_3 -curvature tensor is symmetric in the sense of Carten, then the manifold reduces to the Ricci-symmetric if and only if scalar curvature is constant.

5. CONSERVATIVE PSEUDO W_3 -CURVATURE TENSOR

For conservative, we have Hicks (1965)

$$div \tilde{W}_3 = 0. \tag{5.1}$$

Contracting (4.1) with respect to X , we get

$$(div \tilde{W}_3)(Y, Z)U = (div R)(Y, Z)U - \frac{a}{(n-1)} [(D_Z Ric)(Y, U) - g(Z, U)(div Q)Y]. \tag{5.2}$$

We assume that the manifold is conservative *i.e.* $div \tilde{W}_3 = 0$. Hence from (5.1) and (5.2), we get

$$(div R)(Y, Z)U = \frac{a}{(n-1)} [(D_Z Ric)(Y, U) - g(Z, U)(div Q)Y]. \tag{5.3}$$

It is known that

$$(div R)(Y, Z)U = (D_Y Ric)(Z, U) - (D_Z Ric)(Y, U). \tag{5.4}$$

Therefore, from (5.3) and (5.4), we get

$$(D_Y Ric)(Z, U) - (D_Z Ric)(Y, U) \left(\frac{n-1+a}{n-1}\right) = \frac{-a}{(n-1)} g(Z, U)(div Q)Y. \tag{5.5}$$

Put $Z = U = e_i$ in (5.5), we get

$$dr(Y) = 0, a \neq 0.$$

Thus, we can state the following theorem

Theorem 5.1: Pseudo W_3 -curvature tensor on a Riemannian manifold is divergence free if $dr(Y) = 0$, provided $a \neq 0$.

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